

Closing the Gap in non-Latin script data: An example of git-based pragmatism

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Introduction

In 2021, the Berlin University Alliance (BUA) initiated funding for the project "Closing the Gap in Non-Latin Script Data" (CtG) for a two-year period, which was subsequently extended for an additional three years in 2023. The project's objective was to "develop and coordinate subject-specific infrastructures in the field of DH and research data management for the group of research-intensive regional science and humanities subjects within BUA,"³ with a particular emphasis on non-Latin script (NLS) based data. Given the project's significant emphasis on NLS-based research, it was hosted by the Freie Universität Berlin and situated within the Seminar for Semitic and Arabic Studies.

In an era where nearly all aspects of modern life, from research to communication and administration, are stored and managed through digital services, ensuring the long-term accessibility and preservation of data has become a critical challenge. Despite technological progress, there is an increasing trend of research data and outputs becoming inaccessible or even disappearing entirely after projects conclude. This is often due to a lack of resources—whether financial, human, or infrastructural—as well as the evolving nature of technology, which renders older data formats obsolete. Additionally, economic and political priorities frequently dictate which data are preserved, leading to the neglect of materials perceived as less immediately relevant. These issues are particularly pronounced in the field of NLS research, where limited resources, the perceived political insignificance of its languages, and its categorization as a niche field contribute to a lack of institutional support. However, this challenge extends beyond NLS studies—it raises a broader societal question: how can we ensure that the cultural heritage of our technologically dependent world remains accessible for future generations?

Since this challenge has become more apparent, other projects have also emerged to conduct meta-research on research data management practices. Two notable examples are: B.forscht: Projektbrowser für Altertumswissenschaften⁴ by the Berliner Antike-Kolleg of the Berlin-Branden-

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³ "Closing the Gap in Non-Latin Script Data", Berlin University Alliance, <https://www.berlin-university-alliance.de/en/commitments/research-quality/forschung/ongoing/closing-the-gap/index.html>, accessed October 29, 2024.

⁴ "B.forscht: Projektbrowser für Altertumswissenschaften", Berlin-Brandenburgische Akademie der Wissenschaften, <https://projektbrowser.berliner-antike-kolleg.org/projektbrowser/>, accessed March 18, 2025.

burgische Akademie der Wissenschaften (BBAW), and BUA Open Science Magnifiers⁵, a project hosted at Freie Universität Berlin (FU). B.forscht serves as a catalog of projects related to ancient studies, categorizing them by various aspects such as project type, research region, and topic. Unlike our project, which not only presents research projects but also gathers in-depth data, B.forscht focuses primarily on visibility. Our approach, in contrast, enables a deeper analysis of the field through data-driven methods, allowing us to develop concrete guidelines for improving the sustainability, accessibility, and interoperability of research data. The BUA Open Science Magnifiers project takes a broader perspective by collecting key figures and exemplary Open Science practices from various research areas across BUA partner universities. Their findings are presented in dashboards, including reusable datasets from Charité and the Geosciences Department at FU. The project also collaborates closely with the Berlin Science Survey⁵ (BSS) and has received feedback from over 80 research projects. Unlike our field-specific focus, BUA Open Science Magnifiers addresses Open Science as a general topic, providing cross-disciplinary insights rather than concentrating on a particular research domain.

The relatively short life cycle of research projects has a detrimental impact on research, and thus also on research infrastructure. Similarly, the CtG project faced this challenge. Paradoxically, as is the case with numerous other infrastructure and Research Data Management (RDM)-related projects, for CtG as well a restricted funding period was allocated to developing long-term solutions to the issue of limited project funding. Given the inherent limitations of academic infrastructure and funding policy in ensuring long-term stability for research, employment of researchers, and infrastructure,⁶ the CtG project pursued an alternative approach. If academia is unable to provide the fundamental tools necessary to guarantee the longevity of research and infrastructure, particularly given the constraints of limited contracts that are not amenable to change at the project level, it is imperative to rethink the methods by which research data is created, curated, processed, and stored.

The Project

The project's principal objective is to furnish support and assistance in the development of sustainable solutions for research data. This represents a conventional approach to describing limited RDM-related projects in specific research areas. As the project is hosted at the Seminar for Semitic and Arabic Studies, its initial project focus was on Arabic script, with a wider focus on

⁵ "BUA Open Science Magnifiers", Berlin University Alliance, <https://www.berlin-university-alliance.de/en/commitments/research-quality/forschung/ongoing/dashboard/index.html>, accessed March 18, 2025.

⁶ Most institutions that rely on limited third party funding can neither offer long-term contracts and attractive employment models (see Wagner 2025), nor RDM-solutions that are implementable without RDM-staff that is often affected by the same employment situations, nor technical solutions that offer ways to provide longevity beyond research data archiving, nor offer pragmatic approaches to lightweight solutions of community-based maintenance as for institutional access restrictions. A striking example of such failure of limited funding is described by Dombrowski 2014. Regarding sustainability and longevity in research infrastructure, see also Czolkoß-Hettwer et al 2024.

related scripts such as Hebrew and Syriac. Meanwhile, the scope has expanded considerably, encompassing a total of 114 languages.

In comparison to other analogous projects situated within the extensive range of RDM infrastructure development, the project pursued a distinctive approach. In lieu of the conventional approach of conducting workshops and training for researchers and administering surveys, the team sought to establish a sustainable foundation for developing solutions, or, following the conclusion of the project, a platform upon which other researchers could continue their work independently. Every stage of the process should be conducted in a transparent manner, insofar as ethical considerations permit, thereby providing an exemplar of radical open science⁷ and facilitating comprehension of the team's decisions pertaining to project design, data curation, and the presentation layer. Rather than developing yet another reader for RDM to be lost in institutional repositories, the project work should be visible in any facet, even where it has not succeeded. Ultimately, the project should employ open infrastructure and commit to a sustainable architecture so that it will not be lost without someone taking responsibility for it. From the outset, we sought to ensure that our data would comply with the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) principles⁸ and that the database would not require a traditional server-side infrastructure.

As it transpired, identifying software solutions that could be derived from these principles proved to be a significant challenge. Despite the welcome trend towards greater alignment with Open Access and Open Science principles in academic infrastructure, it proved impossible to identify a single, comprehensive solution, even for the purpose of data storage.

The objective was to ensure the longevity and accessibility of the data. To this end, an accessible standard was selected, enabling individuals with limited technological expertise to comprehend the data structure. The standard should be text-based and thus could be any of the following: XML, JSON, or YAML. We ultimately selected JSON as it aligned more closely with the objective of a lightweight and dynamic front-end interface, while also offering the flexibility to transform it into XML or YAML as export formats in the future. Although XML could be an appropriate choice for our purposes, it is not always suitable for languages written from right to left, such as many of those in our database. In such cases, the tags remain aligned to the left while the text shifts to the right, resulting in an unorganized and confusing layout. Although XML remains the most prevalent file format in DH, our decision to utilize JSON was driven by a desire to present an alternative solution for those who were dissatisfied⁹ with the current standard.

⁷ For us, radical open science means being as transparent and open as possible about our workflows, standards and data. The "radical" stands in opposition to projects and academic encounters that use "open science" as an advertising label. However, there may be limits to openness when it comes to sensitive data, such as in cases covered by GDPR restrictions or, in other contexts, data that could pose a risk to someone.

⁸ "FAIR Principles", GO FAIR, <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles>, accessed October 29, 2024.

⁹ Particularly in non-Latin script-based research, researchers are often dissatisfied with the use of XML, e.g. with Arabic script. Even with editors that support multi-script, XML is often extremely cumbersome, if not unusable, when written in a mixture of right-to-left and left-to-right scripts. What's more, scholars of non-Latin scripts often feel unrepre-

With regard to data storage, we opted for a Git repository. This approach enabled us to leverage the advantages of software engineering workflows while simultaneously documenting each step and offering an option for documented collaboration.

However, this is when the issue first manifested. Although the project was situated at the FU, the user base of other BUA universities had the potential to utilize FU infrastructure as well. However, academic Git repositories, which are often GitLab instances, are typically not accessible to the public. An institutional account is required for both access and collaboration. Moreover, it was not feasible to obtain a project-specific Git instance that was not managed by another institution. Consequently, an alternative solution had to be sought. One objective of the project was to guarantee data accessibility even after the conclusion of funding and to facilitate collaboration with external parties in the development of the database. This was not feasible within the confines of the institutional approach, as evidenced by the case of external researchers without an institutional affiliation who are unable to obtain credentials but could nevertheless contribute value.

We chose GitHub,¹⁰ which is the de facto standard for open-source software projects and is already employed in other open Digital Humanities (DH) initiatives, including those in the domain of NLS research, such as KITAB¹¹ and OpenITI¹². The GitHub platform afforded us the opportunity to utilize a complimentary repository, while its Pages¹³ and Actions¹⁴ features enabled us to implement a streamlined frontend and establish automated workflows, which will be elaborated upon in the subsequent section. Another advantage of GitHub is the existence of the GitHub Archive Program,¹⁵ which permitted the utilization of the Long Term Archiving (LTA)¹⁶ feature without the necessity for the development of proprietary Long Term Archiving (LTA) workflows. The Pages and Actions features would not have been accessible within an institutional repository.

This is one of the initial principal findings of the project. The academic infrastructure is optimal when it aligns with the typical academic workflows. However, when there is a deviation from these established workflows or an openness to integrating with external entities, the infrastructure may not be as effective. It is important to note that the restrictions in academic infrastructure are justified by security concerns, particularly in the context of the growing digital warfare threat.¹⁷ Nev-

sented by Western XML standards, which do not necessarily support non-Western linguistic concepts.

¹⁰ <https://github.com>, accessed October 29, 2024.

¹¹ "KITAB Project Organization", GitHub, <https://github.com/kitab-project-org>, accessed October 29, 2024.

¹² "Open Islamicate Texts Initiative (OpenITI)", GitHub, <https://github.com/OpenITI>, accessed October 29, 2024.

¹³ "GitHub Pages. Websites for you and your projects.", GitHub, <https://pages.github.com>, accessed October 29, 2024.

¹⁴ "GitHub Actions. Automate your workflow from idea to production", GitHub, <https://github.com/features/actions>, accessed October 29, 2024.

¹⁵ "Preserving open source software for future generations", GitHub Archive Program, <https://archiveprogram.github.com>, accessed October 29, 2024.

¹⁶ "Was bedeutet Langzeitarchivierung?", [forschungsdaten.info, https://forschungsdaten.info/themen/veroeffentlichen-und-archivieren/langzeitarchivierung](https://forschungsdaten.info/themen/veroeffentlichen-und-archivieren/langzeitarchivierung), accessed October 29, 2024.

¹⁷ E.g. see the attack on UDE: Knop, Dirk, "Ransomware: Daten von Uni Duisburg-Essen im Darknet, Uni Innsbruck

ertheless, these restrictions may still pose challenges for a project that aims to be accessible to a broader audience beyond the institutional setting.

Consequently, we devised a system that relies on a straightforward GitHub repository in conjunction with a frontend workflow. The database is file-based and structured in a folder, which contains subfolders with simplified project names, each of which contains a data file. The folder structure was selected to facilitate human readability while allowing for the inclusion of data files beyond the standard JSON format. In the event that XML or YAML are to be included as separate file formats in the database, the project files could be collected in their respective folders. Each data file is named with a Universally Unique Identifier (UUID), which is also registered in the data structure as pointing to a specific project. To enhance machine-readability, a top-level JSON register was created that linked the UUIDs to the simplified folder names. This approach enables scripts to access the data via the UUID, while humans can simply read the folder names to navigate to the relevant data.

```
{
  "5e7ab61a-0c33-44fc-8175-a1930e6d08bc": {
    "title": "Automatic Collation for Diversifying Corpora",
    "path": "/PROJECTS/acdc/"
  },
  "b333a11d-b9fc-4379-9e21-fbddd9a9500b1": {
    "title": "Audition Certificates Platform",
    "path": "/PROJECTS/acp/"
  },
  "173631fa-ddc3-4762-bfd9-5bf40ccef41a": {
    "title": "Ada Lovelace Center for Digital Humanities",
    "path": "/PROJECTS/ada_center/"
  },
  "eaf36ccc-5ee4-4749-80ea-7f71f479c968": {
    "title": "Afrikanische Stimmen in islamischen Manuskripten aus Mali: Erschließung und Erforschung afrikanischer Sprachen in arabischer Schrift (Ajami)",
    "path": "/PROJECTS/afrikanische_stimmen_in_islamischen_manuskripten/"
  },
  "46aff246-b6ef-4632-90c2-0993a9f9b1f5": {
    "title": "Arabic Literature Cosmopolitan",
    "path": "/PROJECTS/alc/"
  },
}
```

Fig. 1: An excerpt of the PROJECT.json. (CC-0)

```
├── ARCHIVE
├── CONTRIBUTORS.md
├── DOCS
│   ├── dependencies.md
│   └── meetings_protocol.md
├── KEYWORDS
│   ├── KEYWORDS.json
│   └── KEYWORDS_DOCUMENTATION.md
├── LICENSE
├── PROJECTS
│   ├── .DS_Store
│   ├── a_digital_synopsis_of_the_mishnah_and_tosefta
│   │   └── 71ff37e4-7e16-4c1f-b0a9-9bf47778d41f.json
│   ├── a_digital_typology_of_arabic_documents
│   │   └── 72bf1192-8af5-4df0-bd88-cf4d62d13d66.json
│   ├── acdc
│   │   └── 5e7ab61a-0c33-44fc-8175-a1930e6d08bc.json
│   ├── acp
│   │   └── b333a11d-b9fc-4379-9e21-fbddfa9500b1.json
│   └── PROJECTS.json
├── README.md
├── SCHEMATA
│   ├── changelog.md
│   └── project_schema.ts
├── TEMPLATES
│   └── project.json
├── TESTS
│   ├── find_current.ts
│   ├── language_codes_all.json
│   ├── map_language_codes.ts
│   ├── schema_tests.ts
│   └── utils.ts
└── lychee.toml
```

Fig. 2: An excerpt of the directory tree on GitHub. (CC-0)

Initially, the frontend was constructed in a manner that enabled real-time data access via GET requests. The frontend is constructed using a JavaScript framework (initially Vue¹⁸, subsequently SvelteKit¹⁹), which facilitates the querying and processing of JSON. However, a more traditional build process was subsequently employed, as the intention was to create a complete snapshot of the entire website, rather than just the frontend (this will be discussed in greater detail later). Upon the addition of data to the database, the frontend is rebuilt as a static page, incorporating all of the newly added data.

All data are licensed under a Creative Commons (CC-BY 4.0) license. This is feasible because the data is either collected from publicly accessible sources or obtained through direct contact with researchers, who are interviewed to gain more detailed insights. During these interviews, the researchers are explicitly informed that the data will be released under the aforementioned license. This ensures transparent regulations for subsequent utilization and adherence to the principles of Open Access as outlined in the Berlin Declaration.²⁰

To ensure that all contributors to the project are duly acknowledged, we provide a markdown file delineating the roles assigned according to the Contributor Role Taxonomy (CRediT)²¹, which we maintain in a state of continual updating. Recognizing the contributions of everyone involved is of great relevance for us. We do this in two ways: for employed and voluntary staff, we provide a markdown file that delineates their roles according to the CRediT taxonomy, which we maintain in a state of continual updating. For external contributors, each project file includes metadata that

¹⁸ <https://vuejs.org>, accessed October 29, 2024.

¹⁹ <https://svelte.dev>, accessed October 29, 2024.

²⁰ "Berlin Declaration on Open Access to Knowledge in the Sciences and Humanities", Open Access Initiatives of the Max Planck Society, <https://openaccess.mpg.de/Berlin-Declaration>, accessed October 29, 2024.

²¹ <https://credit.niso.org>, accessed October 29, 2024.

clearly identifies the creator or editor, ensuring that all contributions are transparently documented. Additionally, we furnish human-readable information on the dependencies and software utilized in our workflows.

A distinctive feature of our project is the keyword taxonomy that we have devised for the classification, organization, and visualization of our data. To guarantee interoperability, our approach was to base it on the Digital Humanities Austria (DHA) Taxonomy,²² which was created by the Österreichische Akademie der Wissenschaften. However, since our dataset requires field-specific keywords, such as "Bible," "Koran," or "'isnād," that are not yet included in any existing list of standardized vocabularies, we have elected to extend the DHA-Taxonomy to encompass all aspects relevant to our discipline.

Detailed documentation on the keywords, along with instructions on how to use them properly, is accessible on GitHub alongside a JSON file containing the entire keyword set for those who wish to reuse it or contribute to the project.

It is of the utmost importance that our system for correctly labelling our data is robust, consistent, and interoperable. As our objective is to furnish researchers with assistance and best practices, it is imperative that our data be not only openly accessible but also presented in a straightforward and practical manner, thereby maximizing the benefits that can be derived from it. To this end, the keywords were employed to construct a filter that permits users to search the dataset for specific elements of interest, including output, methodology, sources, or topics. Furthermore, the labelling of this heterogeneous information within each project enables more comprehensive data analysis and the acquisition of deeper insights from the data.

As with the remainder of the data, our objective was to ensure that the taxonomy was both machine- and human-readable. To this end, we selected a standardized notation comprising lowercase and hyphens for spaces, which proved to be the optimal compromise. In addition to the keywords, the research languages utilized in each project are also identified. To guarantee interoperability in this respect, all languages are encoded in accordance with the relevant standards. To facilitate the presentation of insights derived from our data, we have created a series of interactive charts, which are accessible via the frontend. The visualizations display relationships between projects, indicating which are most interconnected and collaborative, as well as their categories and subcategories. This allows for the identification of trends and research interests within the field. Furthermore, the visualization of the languages utilized in the projects and the research institutions within the dataset, along with their involvement in NLS DH, will be un-

²² "DHA Taxonomy", Vocabs, https://vocabs.dariah.eu/dha_taxonomy/en/, accessed October 29, 2024.

dertaken. This will facilitate the identification of potential DH hubs. All charts were constructed using Vega.js,²³ a well-maintained, open-source JavaScript library for data visualization.

Fig. 3: A graph depicting relation between projects. (CC-0)

Fig. 4: A graph depicting categories of projects. (CC-0)

As a general principle, we endeavour to exercise as much transparency and interoperability, and to demonstrate as much commitment to the FAIR principles, as we possibly can with the re-

²³ <https://vega.github.io/vega/>, accessed October 29, 2024.

sources at our disposal. In light of the aforementioned considerations and in alignment with the project's objective, it is our intention to not only establish optimal methodologies for other initiatives but also to exemplify our interpretation of an exemplary approach. We aim to exemplify the principles of openness, transparency, redundancy, and interoperability, collectively known as FAIR, by adhering to them ourselves. This approach has proven effective, particularly in the context of metadata and lightweight text-based formats. However, this is not currently feasible in an academic setting, and our methodology is not without limitations. These considerations will be discussed in greater detail in the "Issues" section.

Workflows and database

As previously described, the file-based database is structured in folders and employs a combination of human-readable simplified project titles as identifiers and UUIDs for machine-readability. The JSON files contain information on a variety of elements.

1. File Metadata: The file metadata includes the date and time of creation, a record of any modifications, the name of the individual responsible for creating or modifying the file, the name of the individual who edited the file, the version of the file schema, and a Boolean field indicating whether the project was subjected to an interview.²⁴

2. Project metadata: This element contains information pertaining to the project, including the title, primary contacts, funding periods, an abbreviation of the title, websites, classification, brief description, location(s), languages, related institutions, other related projects, and numerous other details. It is important to note that the majority of fields have been designed as arrays to allow for multiple entries, for example in relation to funding periods, websites or locations. In general, entities are enhanced with authority control, primarily from the Gemeinsame Normdatei (GND), Wikidata, and Geonames. In this context, the term "languages" refers to the language utilized in the project, whereas the language of the research is documented in a separate field. With regard to the relations, the schema permits the selection of various options, including cooperation or project-sub-project relations, which are applicable to a range of scenarios. The data pertaining to individuals includes a field for the role of the person in the project, classified according to the CRediT taxonomy. The type describes the institutional character of each entry, as we also include research clusters or organizations that do not have a project character.²⁵ In the database, related projects are referenced by their respective UUID. A script can then be used to link two projects via the UUID and the project register file. The aforementioned information is typically accessible online; however, it is not sufficient to fully understand how projects handle their re-

²⁴ In cases where it is convenient, interviews are conducted by staff members. While it would be desirable to have the capacity to conduct interviews for every project, several factors limit this possibility. Firstly, not all projects are currently active. Secondly, there is a lack of available staff to conduct interviews. Thirdly, the project's focus is on voluntary data delivery, rather than on the staff actively seeking out participants.

²⁵ See project characteristics according to ISO 21500.

search data and organize their workflows. To gain this knowledge, we contact and interview the researchers directly. The findings of these interviews are stored in the following sub-elements of the project metadata:

a. Research data metadata: This element contains information pertaining to the research data that a project is generating. The primary element is the language of the research data, represented as an array that typically includes at least one NLS language. Moreover, data pertaining to the sustainability plans and the openness and licensing of the research data are stored here. Additionally, the element contains information regarding the format and standard utilized for the research data, once more in an array format to accommodate the storage of diverse formats.

b. Stack metadata: This element contains information regarding the technology stack, encompassing both the backend and frontend, as well as the utilized database technology and the tools employed. With regard to the tools, supplementary data is stored, including whether they are self-developed, maintained, and accessible. In the future, it is our intention to make the list of tools gathered during the interviews accessible on the front end, primarily with a view to enhancing the visibility of the software solutions developed within the projects included in our database. However, to circumvent the creation of an additional tool directory²⁶ — which would necessitate active maintenance and updates even after the conclusion of our project — we have elected to pursue a more sustainable approach: linking the tools to the WikiProject DH Tool Registry, which was developed by the Scholarly Makers Space at Humboldt University.²⁷ This guarantees that all tools included in our dataset can be identified by a Wikidata authority file, thus relieving us of the obligation to maintain the registry independently.

c. Policies: This element contains information on the research data policy or research data plans of the projects.

d. Keywords: This element contains descriptive keywords from our enhanced taxonomy.

e. Category and comments: The category is included to facilitate grouping on the front end. Examples include "digital_preservation" for projects focused on digitizing, cataloging, or preserving textual data, and "tools_and_analysis" for projects applying or developing digital methods to analyze or process such data. The comments field is intended to provide space for free-text information on the given entry.

²⁶ See Grant, K., Dombrowski, Q., Ranaweera, K., Rodriguez-Arenas, O., Sinclair, S., & Rockwell, G. (2020). Absorbing DiRT: Tool Directories in the Digital Age. *Digital Studies/le Champ Numérique*, 10(1), None. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.16995/dscn.325>.

²⁷ "Wikidata:WikiProject DH Tool Registry", Wikidata, https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:WikiProject_DH_Tool_Registry, accessed October 29, 2024.

In addition to the file metadata, no field is obligatory. However, it is recommended that at least a title, a brief description, and a contact be provided. In the frontend, human-readable descriptive information is employed to provide a succinct card with the most fundamental data. Additional data is used for the purpose of data analysis or the creation of visualizations. In the event that the information is not provided to us or acquired through interviews, we only retain information that is publicly accessible.

The data are ingested in a number of different ways. One possible method for submitting updated data would be to create a pull request and have a team member accept it. In consideration of the post-project period, this could be accomplished by individuals who are dedicated to the project's objective and willing to contribute on a voluntary basis. A second method is to utilize the provided web form to generate a fundamental subset of project information in JSON format. This approach necessitates that personnel process the requests and incorporate the JSON files into the repository. The third method is the most complex and requires the greatest capacity for processing. It involves the creation of a GitHub issue, the sending of an email, or the provision of information through an interview. The information is then to be ingested into the data model and added to the repository. This approach will not be sustainable after the project has ended, as the required capacity in staff cannot be easily acquired on a voluntary basis.

Following the addition of the JSON to the repository, a schema validation is initiated via GitHub actions. The validation is based on the ZOD validation library and is designed to test the formal validity of the ingested data. It is important to note that the aforementioned process does not assess the data content. To ensure the integrity of the data, a manual review is essential, regardless of whether it is conducted via pull request or other ingest pipelines. However, as of the third year of the project, no instances of erroneous data have been identified. Nevertheless, this issue should be considered when contemplating the project's long-term sustainability. In the absence of remunerated personnel, it is imperative that the project be subjected to voluntary quality control measures to ensure its continued integrity. In light of the demonstrated efficacy of this approach in other community-based projects, it seems reasonable to posit that it may prove similarly effective in the case of CtG. Nevertheless, this could also represent a critical juncture at which post-project workflows may no longer function as intended.

The dataset comprises over 1,500 distinct links, including Uniform Resource Locators (URLs) for research institutions and websites for projects and researchers. To guarantee the optimal functionality of each link, we employ the link-checking library Lychee.²⁸ The process of link checking serves a number of purposes. The tool is capable of detecting unstable URLs, which are a common occurrence. It is common for academic content management systems to lack the capacity to provide persistent URLs. Consequently, even a minor alteration to the underlying website struc-

²⁸ <https://lychee.cli.rs>, accessed October 29, 2024.

ture can render previously indexed content inaccessible. Furthermore, the tool can detect instances where websites are undergoing a temporary suspension. This is often indicative of a lack of long-term funding and an unsustainable academic infrastructure. Frequently, after the conclusion of a project, the associated website is simply terminated. In the absence of a plan or resources to ensure its continued functionality, the website is effectively destined for obsolescence.

Although RDM plans often include consideration of these aspects, projects tend not to devote sufficient attention to post-project infrastructural perspectives. Demonstrating the issue of project websites becoming inaccessible or obsolete is enabling us to make a political statement about the necessity of ensuring longevity for the presentational layer as well. Research websites serve as a conduit through which research is consumed, processed, and discussed. As such, they constitute a vital component of a project's output and must be preserved.

Our web presence is guaranteed to remain online for the duration of GitHub's operational lifespan. However, relying on a single provider is not a sustainable strategy. Consequently, we devised a strategy to guarantee the continued availability and functionality of not only our data, but also our frontend. The most straightforward method for achieving this is to create regular snapshots of the page. As previously discussed, it is essential to have a static frontend to capture not only the frontend's structure but also the data it displays. This static format enables us to save monthly snapshots to the Internet Archive. In the event that the website becomes inaccessible in the future due to GitHub's decision to terminate the repository, it would still be possible to access the website through the Wayback Machine.²⁹

A third potential option is the periodic publication of the entire data set on Zenodo.³⁰ In addition to the data and the frontend, the complete project is released on a regular basis, typically coinciding with the implementation of minor or major updates. This enables the project to be referenced as a whole with a stable Digital Object Identifier (DOI), thereby providing a backup solution. The complete website can be readily downloaded and installed on a local machine, a web server, or even a new repository with integrated page functionality. Another advantage of this tripartite preservation strategy is that it allows us to avail ourselves of the GitHub Archive Program in collaboration with the Internet Archive and the Software Heritage Foundation.³¹ In conclusion, the data and project folder are preserved via releases and repository archiving, and a way is provided for the website to remain usable even after the project has ended, at least as long as GitHub or

²⁹ "Closing the Gap in Non-Latin Script Data", Wayback Machine, https://web.archive.org/web/20240000000000*/https://m-l-d-h.github.io/Closing-The-Gap-In-Non-Latin-Script-Data, accessed October 29, 2024.

³⁰ Theo Beers, Jonas Müller-Laackman, Xenia Monika Kudela, Maroussia, & Mathew Barber. (2024). M-L-D-H/Closing-The-Gap-In-Non-Latin-Script-Data: v1.3.0 (v1.3.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12579502>

³¹ "Closing the Gap in Non-Latin Script Data", Software Heritage Archive, https://archive.software-heritage.org/browse/origin/directory/?origin_url=https://github.com/M-L-D-H/Closing-The-Gap-In-Non-Latin-Script-Data, accessed October 29, 2024.

any other similar provider offers a pages functionality or the Wayback Machine functions. As this is a relatively straightforward process, it could easily be incorporated into other project workflows.

It is apparent that we integrate existing RDM solutions, such as Zenodo, to enhance the sustainability of our data. However, these should not be seen as alternatives to our approach. Unlike platforms like Dataverse and CKAN, which focus on structured data storage and retrieval, or Zenodo, which provides DOI-based archiving, our project offers an interactive website with a dynamic and complex system for displaying and categorizing research data. This level of interactivity and structured visualization would not be possible within these existing models, as they primarily function as repositories rather than as adaptive research tools.

Issues

Our project pipelines are not yet optimal, as we have yet to fully leverage the potential of existing open, free, and accessible infrastructure. While our workflows could be readily adapted for use in other research projects, ensuring improved sustainability, there are inherent limitations to our current approach.

A significant challenge is the heavy reliance on GitHub. As a Microsoft-owned platform, GitHub is a product of a major technology company. Although this allows for free usage, provides a platform with a vast user base and is aligned with industry standards, it also gives rise to certain political issues. It is not prudent for academic activities to rely on the goodwill of a major technology company and its services.³² In the event of Microsoft's decision to terminate GitHub, the majority of our workflows would be irretrievably lost. However, GitHub is not the sole provider of such services. In the future, it may be prudent to consider migrating to an alternative, NGO-based solution such as Codeberg.³³ This would enhance independence from Big Tech and support for independent providers, but it would also entail the loss of the GitHub archive, at least if we do not develop an archiving pipeline ourselves.

A second issue is that our data remains entirely accessible in its current form. There are numerous reasons why one might hesitate to open the data to the extent that we did, including concerns about unwanted AI training, data misuse, and the issue of sensitive data. This is a pervasive issue inherent to a radical open science approach. As our project content is licensed under CC-BY, we should be appropriately identified when the project data is utilized. Ultimately, however, this is beyond our control. Consequently, the workflows developed for the storage, presentation, and

³² This is becoming increasingly important in light of recent developments under the second Trump administration. Not only can academia not rely on Big Tech companies to resist authoritarian influence, but it must rather be aware of its kneefall before authoritarian politics. This paper was written in autumn 2024 and revised in early 2025. Political developments offer a perspective that may make our reliance on GitHub unsustainable, and a migration to institutional (open) GitLabs or independent non-profit organisations like Codeberg necessary.

³³ <https://codeberg.org>, accessed October 29, 2024.

archiving of research data cannot be implemented in projects that involve the handling of sensitive data.³⁴

Ultimately, the necessity for a lightweight structure may present a challenge for projects involving more intricate, relational data. This is a pervasive issue in file-based databases, and the database would undoubtedly demonstrate enhanced performance in a more robust database configuration. Nevertheless, if we can maintain the integrity of our data model, our approach can be regarded as a compromise that facilitates enhanced sustainability while remaining accessible and sufficiently performative for our requirements.

The current limitations of our database approach, including the absence of a comprehensive index and the lack of an Application Programming Interface (API)-based integration with other knowledge graphs, could be addressed by replicating our data within existing knowledge bases such as Wikidata. As previously discussed, our objective is to establish a connection between our data and the tool repository on Wikidata. The subsequent step would be to develop a regular pipeline for mirroring the entire project data set to Wikidata. This would permit the assignment of persistent identifiers to the datasets, which could then be referenced in our data. It would also facilitate the accessibility of our data for SPARQL queries on Wikidata. Furthermore, users would be able to establish connections within a larger knowledge graph, enabling them to respond to queries such as: Which projects have utilized which tools for a given language? Is there anyone who has previously interacted with this tool before in a comparable context, with whom I could consult? Is my approach also applicable to other scripts or languages? Furthermore, an additional backup for the data storage would be established, although the possibility of implementing a focused quality control process would be eliminated. In terms of resources and staff capacity, it would be more optimal to focus on either Wikidata or GitHub as the data storage, given that we have yet to implement and test Wikidata as a data storage option for our complete data set.

Another way to improve accessibility and interoperability is to offer the dataset as RDF (Resource Description Framework) or CSV (Comma-Separated Values) for direct download, or ideally with an API. Providing an RDF export would allow seamless integration with other linked data environments, making it easier for researchers to query and connect our dataset to external knowledge graphs beyond Wikidata. A CSV option, on the other hand, would ensure compatibility with a wider range of research workflows, particularly for those working with statistical or relational database tools. By enabling both formats, we could support different use cases, from semantic web applications to traditional data analysis. However, such static exports would lack the dy-

³⁴ In addition, it could be argued that our approach has limitations for complex data requiring complex database systems. We would argue that most metadata and text-based projects could adopt a file-based approach, either as barebones as ours or with an added lightweight database layer to allow better querying. They could also adopt a wikidata-based approach, allowing SPARQL querying of our data. However, large projects with highly complex or multimodal data may require the development of an additional set of pipelines to handle their data while remaining as open, lightweight and transparent as our approach. In the end, we don't propose a perfect solution, but an exemplary one that can and should be extended and adapted to specific project needs.

dynamic, interactive features of a proper API (e.g. based on the OpenAPI standards).³⁵ However, such a service is not possible with our current capabilities and may require a different stack and/or setup. Consequently, evaluating these options remains a task for the more distant future.

Conclusion

We have presented our principal workflows and tenets and demonstrated methods by which extant infrastructure, even (or particularly) that which exists outside the domain of institutional academia, can assist in the storage, organisation and preservation of data in a sustainable manner and in alignment with the FAIR principles. Nevertheless, this cannot be considered a solution to the sustainability and longevity issues currently facing academia. It is imperative that academia acknowledges its shortcomings, responds to the call for change, and develops a genuinely open and sustainable infrastructure that enables the growth of similarly open initiatives like ours. It is only if academia can provide such infrastructure in a way that is not onerous and can adapt to the requirements of open science that it will be able to undergo a genuine digital transformation.

Furthermore, academic infrastructure and administration must ensure that openness is not merely a desirable attribute but an indispensable component of research, particularly in cases where the data in question does not pertain to matters of ethical sensitivity or personal information that cannot be published. Even in such instances, it is feasible to devise pipelines that can remain open to a considerable extent.

In an ideal world, academia would provide solutions akin to GitHub, offering pages and actions, collaboration opportunities for external parties, and an accessible storage system for files and data. In order to achieve this, academia must move beyond its current exclusive focus on institutional or consortial initiatives. It must undergo a transformation into a digital service provider.³⁶

As previously discussed, our pipelines represent an optimal approach for text- or metadata-based projects that do not involve the processing of sensitive or complex data. We are engaged in an ongoing process of workflow optimisation, seeking to identify novel and enhanced methods for addressing sustainability-related challenges in academic research. By adopting this "practice what we preach" approach, we are charting a distinct course in the realm of research data management (RDM) projects. Our aim is to demonstrate that it is feasible to consistently adhere to the tenets of open science, open access, and data that is findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) without becoming overly preoccupied with the intricacies of infrastructure. As

³⁵ <https://github.com/OAI/OpenAPI-Specification/tree/main>, accessed March 2025.

³⁶ Current initiatives to offer Data Spaces, like the European Open Science Cloud, are a step in the right direction. However, they are not equally valuable for data-driven research approaches that follow git workflows. Most cloud solutions, as well as most research data repositories, offer space and tools for collaboration and storage, but lack to provide a collaborative development environment. Git repositories like GitHub, GitLab, or Codeberg, are specifically designed for these tasks. However, a European, National, or even communal solution for research projects aiming for open, transinstitutional, dev-based approaches that remain work in progress by design, like CtG, is yet to be introduced.

this is also the fundamental challenge of academic infrastructure, we aim to demonstrate the necessity for academia to undergo a transformation that simplifies the setup and access to infrastructure, both for internal and external researchers, in order to facilitate collaboration at the operational level.

The project will conclude in 2026. If our pipelines are able to provide the solutions we anticipate, this will be evident at the conclusion of the project, following the departure of the majority of the project team and the subsequent reliance on voluntary contributions to maintain the CtG database. However, even if the project is ultimately discontinued, the pipeline will remain accessible for an extended period.

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